

ECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF MARKETING ASPECT OF CUMIN AND FENNEL IN NORTH GUJARAT REGION

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MS Received: 18.05.2024; MS Revised: 15.06.2024; MS Accepted: 16.06.2024

MS 3208

(RESEARCH PAPER IN AGRICULTURAL ECONOMICS,.)

Abstract

The present investigation was carried out to analyse the marketing aspects of cumin and fennel in Banaskantha and Mehsana districts of North Gujarat region, which were selected based on higher area. Primary data were utilized in the study. A sample of 144 farmers (72 of each crop) was selected using multistage random sampling, and 24 market functionaries were selected from the study area. Among major marketing channels, channel-II (producer-wholesaler/commission agent – retailer-consumer) was most popular because of less number of intermediaries involved and about 95.83 percent and 94.44 percent of total quantity of cumin and fennel respectively was sold through this channel. An average marketing cost incurred by cumin farmers was ₹220.88 per quintal, among different cost, packing charges was highest (27.96%). The marketing cost incurred by retailers (₹568.7) per quintal of cumin was higher than wholesaler/commission agent (₹480.60). The producer's share in consumer's rupee was 73.96 percent and price spread was ₹4134.25 per quintal of cumin. In case of fennel, average marketing cost incurred by farmers was ₹164.95 per quintal; cost of preparation of produce for market was highest (28.65%) followed by packing charges (27.33%). The marketing cost incurred by retailers (₹500.01) was higher than wholesaler/commission agents (₹380.75). Retailers of both the commodities earned higher margin than wholesaler/commission agents. The producer's share in consumer's rupee was 68.81 percent and price spread was ₹3780.71 per quintal. The marketing efficiency was greater than unity for both cumin (2.84) and fennel (2.20) indicates the existence of efficient marketing systems in the study area. Cumin and fennel are important spice crop in North Gujarat. Majority of the cumin and fennel growers sold their farm produce to the regulated markets through channel-II. Per quintal marketing cost incurred and margin earned by retailers was higher than wholesaler-cum-commission agents (channel-II). The marketing efficiency was greater than unity for both crops reveals efficient marketing system in the study area.

Keywords: cumin, fennel, marketing channel, marketing cost, price spread, marketing efficiency

Introduction

India has the largest domestic market for spices in the world and known as the 'The home of spices'. India is the world's largest producer, consumer and exporter of seed spices; the country produces about 75 of the 109 varieties listed by the International Standards Organization (ISO) and accounts for half of the global trading in spices. India produced 9.754 million tonnes of spices from an area of 4.138 million hectares and exported 1.193 million tonnes during 2019-20. Among the common spices, seed spices are known as low volume high value crops. The seed spices are well distributed over different agro-climatic regions in India. But the major belt spread from semi-arid to arid covering larger area in Gujarat and Rajasthan. Gujarat state is contributing 16.89 percent (0.699 million hectares) of total spice area and 10.35 percent (1.009 million tonnes) of total spices production of country and the state is at top most in India so far as the production of seed spices is concerned (Anonymous, 2019). Among the seed spices cumin and fennel are the most popular cash crops of North Gujarat and the economy of the region depends to a considerable extent on these crops due to short duration nature and greater potential to grow to gets better income compared to other traditional crops. Therefore, the present study was undertaken to find out prevailing marketing channels, to find out marketing cost incurred by the farmers and market functionaries, margins earned by them, price spread, marketing efficiency and producer's share in consumer's purchase price for cumin and fennel in the study area.

Data and Methodology

The present study was conducted at North Gujarat region of the state. This region comprises of seven districts, among them Banaskantha and Mehsana districts were purposively selected for the study based on higher area under cultivation. The primary data were collected for the year 2019-20. Primary data regarding the farm size, cost of inputs, yield, cost involved in sale of produce, constraints faced by farmer-producers and cost incurred by market functionaries were collected by using well designed pre-tested interview schedule. Further, at successive stages talukas, villages and sample farmers were chosen by adopting multistage random sampling technique. Three talukas from each selected districts viz., Tharad, Deodar and Dhanera from Banaskantha district and Kadi, Bechraji and Mehsana from Mehsana district, two villages from each selected talukas and from each selected villages twelve farmers were chosen randomly. Thus, total of

144 sample farmers (2×3×2×12) were taken and total of 24 market functionaries i.e., 12 wholesaler cum commission agent and 12 retailers were selected from Unjha, Palanpur and Tharad regulated markets for study by using simple random sampling method.

Analytical tools**Marketing channels**

There were two marketing channel involved in the sale of cumin and fennel:

Channel – I Producer – Village trader – Wholesaler – Retailer – Consumer (village sale)

Channel-II Producer – Wholesaler/commission agent – Retailer – Consumer (mandi sale)

Marketing costs

The total cost incurred on marketing of cumin and fennel crop by the sample farmers and the intermediaries involved in the process of marketing were calculated by using following formula:

$$MC = C_F + C_{m1} + C_{m2} + C_{m3} + \dots + C_{mn}$$

Where,

MC = Total Marketing cost (₹ quintal⁻¹)

C_F = Cost incurred by the farmer-producer in marketing of farm produce (₹ quintal⁻¹)

C_{mi} = Cost incurred by the ith middleman in the process of buying and selling of the product (₹ quintal⁻¹)

Marketing margin

Profits of the various market functionaries i.e., wholesaler/commission agent and retailer involved in the process of movement of produce from farmers to the final consumer.

Absolute margin of the ith middlemen (A_{mi})

$$= (S_{pi} - (P_{pi} + C_{mi}))$$

Where,

S_{pi} = Sale price per unit quantity of good (₹ quintal⁻¹)

P_{pi} = Purchase price per unit quantity of good (₹ quintal⁻¹)

C_{mi} = Cost incurred in marketing (₹ quintal⁻¹)

Producer's net price

The net price received by the producer farmer at the time of first sale of farm produce.

$$\text{Producer's Price (P}_F) = P_A - C_F$$

Where,

P_A = Wholesale price in the primary assembling market (₹ quintal⁻¹)

C_F = marketing cost incurred by the farmer (₹ quintal⁻¹)

Price spread

It is the difference between the price paid by the consumer and the net price received by the producer for an equivalent quantity of farm produce.

$$\text{Price spread} = P_C - P_F$$

Where,

P_C = Consumer's purchase price/Retailer's sale price (₹ quintal⁻¹)

P_F = Producer's net price (₹ quintal⁻¹)

Producer's share in consumer's rupee

It is the price received by the farmer expressed as a percentage of the paid by the consumer's purchase price.

$$P_S = \frac{P_F}{P_C} \times 100$$

Where,

P_S = Producer's share in the consumer's rupee (₹ quintal⁻¹)

P_C = Consumer's purchase price/retailer's sale price (₹ quintal⁻¹)

P_F = Producer's net price (₹ quintal⁻¹)

Marketing Efficiency

For measuring the Marketing Efficiency, the Shepherd's (Shepherd, 1965) formula was used as given below:

$$ME = \frac{V}{I} - 1$$

Where,

ME = Marketing efficiency

V = Total value of goods sold

I = Total marketing costs

Results and Discussion

Marketing channels of cumin and fennel

It can be seen from the table 1 that two major marketing channels were dominated in sale of cumin and fennel:

channel-I : Producer – village trader – wholesaler – retailer – consumer

channel-II : Producer –wholesaler/commission agent – retailer – consumer

Table 1 Marketing channels of cumin and fennel in North Gujarat region

Marketing channel	Channel	% of total quantity sold of cumin	% of total quantity sold of fennel
Producer – Village trader – Wholesaler – Retailer – Consumer (village sale)	I	4.17	5.56
Producer – Wholesaler/commission agent – Retailer – Consumer (mandi sale)	II	95.83	94.44
	Total:	100.00	100.00

Among these, channel-II was most popular than channel-I because of less number of intermediaries involved in marketing and about 95.83 percent and 94.44 percent of total quantity of cumin and fennel, respectively was sold through this channel. Similar results were obtained by Verma and Kumar (2015), Trambadiya (2016) for cumin crop, Sharma and Dhaka (2018) for coriander and cumin crop. Thus, among these two channels of cumin and fennel marketing, channel-II (producer-wholesaler/commission agent- retailer- consumer) is involved in further findings of the study.

Marketing cost incurred by farmer-producers (channel-II)

On an average marketing cost incurred by cumin farmers amounted to ₹ 220.88 per quintal. Among the various components of marketing

cost, packing charges (including cost of gunny bags) was highest (27.96%) followed by preparation of produce for market (27.12%), transportation cost (24.24%), loading and unloading charges (14.94%) and other expenses (5.74%). Average marketing cost incurred by fennel farmers was ₹ 164.95 per quintal. Among the various components of marketing costs, cost of preparation of produce for market was highest (28.65%) followed by packing charges (including cost of gunny bags), transportation cost, loading and unloading charges, and other expenses which accounted for about 27.33, 20.92, 16.87 and 6.23 percent, respectively.

Table 2 Marketing cost incurred by cumin and fennel farmers on the sample farms (₹ qtl⁻¹)

Sr. No.	Particulars	Cumin		Fennel	
		₹ qtl ⁻¹	% to total cost	₹ qtl ⁻¹	% to total cost
	Producer's sale price/ wholesaler's purchase price	11962.56	-	8507.46	-
1.	Preparation for market	59.90	27.12	47.25	28.65
2.	Loading and unloading charges	33.00	14.94	27.83	16.87
3.	Packing charges Gunny bags	61.75	27.96	45.08	27.33
4.	Transportation cost	53.55	24.24	34.50	20.92
5.	Other expenses	12.68	5.74	10.28	6.23
	Total marketing cost	220.88	100.00	164.95	100.00

Marketing cost incurred by wholesaler cum commission agent

The details about marketing cost incurred by wholesaler-cum-commission agent and retailer in the marketing of cumin and fennel are presented in Table 3. The total marketing cost borne by wholesaler-cum-commission agent for cumin was ₹ 480.60 qtl⁻¹ and for fennel, it was ₹ 380.75 qtl⁻¹. Among the various cost components of cumin, commission charges accounted for about 39.42 per cent of total marketing cost, followed by spoilage (14.60%), and local tax

(14.53%) etc., and the cost components of fennel marketing at wholesaler-cum-commission agent level indicates that the commission charges ranked first accounting for 36.14 per cent, followed by grading and packing (16.09%) and spoilage (15.57%) etc., Moreover, the marketing cost incurred by wholesaler-cum-commission agent was higher in cumin as compared to fennel because of high magnitude of commission charges and spoilage.

Table 3: Marketing cost incurred by wholesaler-cum-commission agents and retailers

Marketing cost incurred by wholesaler-cum-commission agents					
Sr. No.	Particulars	Cumin		Fennel	
		₹ qtl ⁻¹	% to total cost	₹ qtl ⁻¹	% to total cost
	Wholesaler's sale price/ Retailer's purchase price	13195.16	-	9403.21	-
1.	Transportation cost	29.00	6.03	27.00	7.09

2.	Grading and packing	65.00	13.52	61.25	16.09
3.	Loading and unloading	36.00	7.91	36.50	9.59
4.	Local tax	69.80	14.53	52.54	13.80
5.	Commission	189.44	39.42	137.61	36.14
6.	Spoilage	70.15	14.60	59.30	15.57
7.	Other expenses	19.20	4.00	6.55	1.72
	Total marketing cost	480.60	100.00	380.75	100.00
Marketing cost incurred by retailers					
	Retailer's sale price/ Consumer's purchase price	15875.93	-	12123.22	-
1.	Transportation cost	49.00	8.62	55.00	11.00
2.	Grading and packing	91.00	16.00	86.00	17.20
3.	Loading and unloading	40.00	7.03	42.00	8.40
4.	Local tax	72.22	12.70	54.44	10.89
5.	Commission	196.55	34.56	143.32	28.66
6.	Spoilage	83.90	14.75	81.00	16.20
7.	Other expenses	36.10	6.35	38.25	7.65
	Total marketing cost	568.77	100.00	500.01	100.00

Marketing cost incurred by retailers

The total marketing costs incurred by retailers of cumint was found ₹ 568.77 per quintal. Among different items of expenditure, the maximum share was noticed for commission charges 34.56% to total marketing cost. In case of fennel, the total marketing cost incurred by retailers amounted to ₹ 500.01 per quintal. Among different components, share of commission was highest (28.66%), followed by grading and packing charges (17.20%). Further, it was found that the marketing cost at retailer's level was higher in cumint as compared to fennel due to higher commission.

Marketing margin and price spreads

Table 4: Marketing cost, margins and price spread of cumint and fennel for channel II

Sr. No.	Particulars	Cumint		Fennel	
		₹ qtl ⁻¹	% of consumer's purchase price	₹ qtl ⁻¹	% of consumer's purchase price
1.	Producer's net price	11741.68	73.96	8342.51	68.81
2.	Cost incurred by				
	(a) Producer	220.88	1.39	164.95	1.36
	(b) Wholesaler-cum-commission agent	480.60	3.03	380.75	3.14
	(c) Retailer	568.77	3.58	500.01	4.13
	Total:	1270.25	8.00	1045.71	8.63
3.	Margins of				
	(a) Wholesaler-cum-commission agent	752.00	4.74	515.00	4.25
	(b) Retailer	2112.00	13.30	2220.00	18.31
	Total:	2864.00	18.04	2735.00	22.56
4.	Price spread (cost + margins)	4134.25	26.04	3780.71	31.19
5.	Retailer's sale price/consumer's purchase price	15875.93	100.00	12123.22	100.00

In case of fennel, total marketing cost borne by different functionaries was ₹ 1045.71 qtl⁻¹, which accounted for 8.63 per cent of the consumer's price. Distribution of total marketing cost among different functionaries viz., producers, wholesalers-cum commission agents and retailers was 1.36, 3.14 and 4.13 per cent, respectively. Moreover, the data inferred that total marketing margins earned by different functionaries involved in the marketing of fennel was ₹ 2735 qtl⁻¹. The share of wholesalers-cum commission agents and retailers in that margin was 4.25 and 18.31 per cent, respectively. The producer's share in consumer's rupee was 68.81 per cent in marketing of one quintal of fennel.

Table 5: Marketing efficiency of cumint and fennel

Sr. No.	Particulars	Cumint	Fennel
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The total margin earned by different functionaries was ₹ 2864 qtl⁻¹ of cumint. It was higher at retailer's level (₹ 2112 qtl⁻¹) compared to wholesaler (₹ 752 qtl⁻¹), constituting 13.30 and 4.74 per cent of consumer's price, respectively. The total marketing cost incurred by different functionaries was ₹ 1270.25 qtl⁻¹ for cumint accounting for 8.00 per cent of the consumer's purchase price. Out of total marketing cost, the highest cost (3.58%) was incurred by retailers followed by wholesaler-cum-commission agents (3.00%) and producers (1.39%). Further, it was observed from the table that producer's share in consumer's rupee was 73.96 per cent.

Marketing efficiency of cumint and fennel

The marketing efficiency of cumint and fennel was worked out by using Shepherd's formula. A perusal of Table 5 reveals that, the sum of marketing cost and marketing margins involved in the selected marketing channel (channel II) was ₹ 4134.25 qtl⁻¹ and ₹ 3780.71 qtl⁻¹ respectively. Considering this with producer's net price per quintal, the marketing efficiency was higher than unity (2.84). Moreover, marketing efficiency for fennel was 2.20. Thus, the index of marketing efficiency was greater than unity for both cumint as well as fennel indicates the existence of efficient marketing systems. Similar findings was observed by Bareliya *et al.* (2022) for coriander crop.

1.	Consumer's price (₹ qtl ⁻¹)	15875.93	12123.22
2.	Producer's net price (₹ qtl ⁻¹)	11741.68	8342.51
3.	Marketing cost (₹ qtl ⁻¹)	1270.25	1045.71
4.	Marketing margin (₹ qtl ⁻¹)	2864.00	2735.00
5.	Marketing efficiency (%)	2.84	2.20

Conclusion

The study reveals that, major two marketing channels were identified in the study area (North Gujarat region). Most of the farmer-producers of cumin and fennel crop sold their farm produce directly to the regulated markets (APMCs) through channel-II (Producer – wholesaler/commission agent – retailer – consumer). Per quintal marketing cost incurred by retailers was higher than wholesaler-cum-commission agents in marketing of both the commodities. Marketing margin earned by retailers was higher than wholesaler-cum-commission agent as retailers add value through packaging, branding, and direct consumer access, enabling them to charge a higher price, while wholesalers primarily facilitate distribution without these added value components. The share of producer's in consumer's purchase price was observed higher in cumin (73.96%) as compared to fennel crop (68.81%). The index of marketing efficiency was greater than unity for cumin (2.84) and fennel (2.20) indicates existence of efficient marketing system.

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